

Knowledge Management for Intelligent Systems

J.UCS Special Issue

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This special issue of the *Journal of Universal Computer Science* contains selected and extended papers presented at the *Third International Symposium on Agent and Multi-agent Systems: Technology and Applications (KES-AMSTA 2009)*, which was successfully held in Uppsala, Sweden, June 3 – 5, 2009. This symposium was the successful third event in the international symposium series on Agent and Multi-agent Systems, chaired by N.T. Nguyen and supported by KES International. The second group of papers consists of 9 papers which are selected and extended versions from the presentations at *2008 International Conference on Intelligent Computing*, held on September 15–18, 2008 in Shanghai, China, and chaired by D.S. Huang and K.H. Jo. For both conferences the proceedings were published by Springer in the prestigious series LNCS/LNAI. The third group of papers consists of several invited papers. All submitted papers have been thoroughly reviewed by three well known specialists in the fields in a double-blind mode and only those with the highest scores have been accepted.

We cordially thank the reviewers for their valuable reviews, which guarantee the high quality of the accepted papers. Special thanks go to the authors for their contributions to this special issue. Finally, we would like to thank Professor Hermann Maurer, the Managing Editor of J.UCS, and Dana Kaiser for their supports in editing this issue.

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